

The "shocking" interaction between supernova remnants and molecular clouds

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Massive stars ($M \geq 8 M_{\odot}$) drive powerful stellar feedback that profoundly affects the evolution and star formation efficiency (SFE) of the hosting galaxies. Among these mechanisms, feedback driven by supernova explosions (SNe) are some of the most energetic [1] and long-lasting [2, 3], and therefore among the most effective. As the remnant (SNR) expands, the hot plasma pushes and compresses outwards the atomic and molecular gas in contact with the remnant [4] and injects energy, mass and momentum into the interstellar medium (ISM), profoundly affecting its physical and chemical properties [5]. At the typical cloud spatial scales (< 10 pc), SNRs drive slow shock compression that impact onto nearby pre-existent molecular clouds and locally enhance the density of the molecular material [6, 7]. This increases the gas turbulence and eventually triggers the formation of new stars [8, 9]. It has been shown that SNR-cloud interactions can enhance cloud SFE in nearby galaxies up to $> 40\%$ [10]. It is thus important to observationally investigate the effects that supernova feedback has on the molecular phase of the ISM, i.e., the material that primarily fuels star formation in galaxies. The study of SNR-cloud interactions can enable a better understanding of the star formation enhancement and suppression in the ISM.

Figure 1: Three-color image showing the position of W44 (blue circle) with respect to G034.77-00.55 (black circle). A nearby Hii region is also indicated (green circle). Red is $24 \mu\text{m}$ emission (Spitzer MIPS GAL) [11], green is $8 \mu\text{m}$ emission (Spitzer GLIMPSE) [12], and blue shows a combined JVLA +GBT 21 cm continuum map (THOR survey) [13]. The white square indicates the ALMA mosaic area.

The W44-G034 shock interaction.

Among the best known sites of SNR-cloud interaction is the one occurring between the SNR W44 and the nearby Infrared Dark Cloud (IRDC) G034.77-00.55 (hereafter, G034) [14, 15, 16]. In Figure 1, the relative location of W44 and G034 is shown. The expansion of the 20k years old core-collapse SNR pushes away the surrounding molecular material that interacts with the pre-existing IRDC [6]. Towards this region, we have used the silicon monoxide SiO(2-1) emission at 86.6 GHz, to study the morphology, dynamic and kinematics of the shocked molecular gas [17, 6]. SiO is a unique shock tracer, whose abundance is usually very low in quiescent regions, but becomes extremely enhanced in the presence of shocks, where dust sputtering occurs [18, 19, 20].

Figure 2: SiO integrated intensity map (black contours; velocity range $36.6\text{--}47.6 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) toward G034 superimposed on its first moment velocity map (red scale). Contours are from 3σ ($\sigma=0.016 \text{ Jy km s}^{-1}$) by steps of 3σ . The $A_v > 20$ mag dense material in the IRDC is indicated as green contour and shadow [21]. The beam size is indicated as a black ellipse in the bottom left corner.

The SiO emission toward the W44-G034 interactions site is shown in Figure 2 as mapped at high-angular resolution with the Atacama Large Millimetre/sub-millimetre Array (ALMA). The shocked gas emission is organised into two elongated structures caught in the act of decelerating (from $\sim 46 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ to $\sim 39 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and plunging into

a dense ridge at the edge of G034. This behaviour is similar to that of a sea wave (the shocks) plunging and breaking into a sandy shore (the cloud dense ridge). Towards the dense ridge, no signature of ongoing star formation activity that may account for the observed SiO emission are found. As seen from multiple C¹⁸O transitions (IRAM-30m), the shock propagation enhances the gas density within the ridge to values $n(\text{H}_2) > 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, compatible to those required to enable star formation [22]. The momentum injected into the dense shocked gas is estimated to be $\sim 20 M_{\odot} \text{ km s}^{-1}$ [6].

Figure 3: Logo of the SHREC survey. Credit: Giulia Zora.

SHREC: SHock interaction between supernova REmnants and molecular Clouds

In order to extend the study of feedback driven by SNRs in molecular clouds, we have initiated the exploratory ESO-ARO large program SHREC i.e. SHock interactions between supernova REmnants and molecular Clouds (P.I. Cosentino; Figure 3). SHREC uses the 12m antenna at the Arizona Radio Observatory (ARO) to detect SiO(2-1), H¹³CO⁺(1-0) and HN¹³C(1-0) emission towards a sample of 27 SNRs. These sources are located relatively nearby (kinematic distance ≤ 6 kpc) and show previous evidence of interaction with the surrounding molecular material [23, 24], i.e., enhanced X-ray emission, the presence of OH maser emission, and enhanced CO(2-1)/CO(1-0) ratios [5]. The final goal of SHREC is to identify sites of large-scale interactions driven by SNRs and to investigate how these affect the star formation potential and dispersal of the surrounding molecular material (Cosentino et al., in prep.).

Conclusions

We have used the unique capability of ALMA to investigate the morphology, dynamic and kinematic structure of the shocked gas emission toward the W44-G034 interaction site. We find that the shocked gas morphology resemble that of plane-parallel shock front driven by W44 and plunging into the dense ridge at the edge of the cloud. The shock propagation through the molecular material efficiently compress the gas, increasing its densities to values comparable to those required for the formation of massive stars. The high-angular resolution achieved also allows to pierce into the internal physical structure of the shock, providing optimal tools to test our current MHD shock theories. It is therefore necessary to extend the sample of SNR-cloud interaction sites seen by shock molecular tracers to evaluate their relevance in setting the initial conditions for star formation in the ISM.

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